

Female Foeticide- A Perspective and Problem

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Abstract

The importance of sexual inequality is often felt at the instance of the birth of a child. The first question parents ask at the birth of a child, in all societies all over the world is always the same, "is it a boy or a girl?" in fact the inequality of the sexes is probably the oldest form of structural social inequality. India is a land of religion where the girl is seen as an incarnation of Goddess 'Laxmi'. True many families are out of bounds in joy when a girl child is born in their family. They think she will bring luck, harmony, happiness and peace in their family. But in India, a most brutal form of killing females take place regularly even before they have the opportunity to be born. Female foeticide in India is the act of killing the female fetus outside of the legal channels of abortion. Female foeticide is still prevalent in Indian society; in fact, it has been a practice for hundreds of years. Narrow-minded people do not mind murdering unborn daughter for fear of giving huge amounts of dowry at the time of her marriage. The birth of a girl child is often seen as a curse to the family and the child is considered as a major burden to the parents. Some people could say that this belief was true in the past, but it is not true of the current modern times where the girls are given equal opportunity in education. Still, our country is in practice of killing an unborn female baby. Female foeticide is the selective abortion of female fetuses to killing upwards of one million females annually. Female foeticide is a relatively new practice, emerging concurrently with the advent of technological advancements in parental sex determination on a large scale in the 1990s. While abortion is legal in India, it is a crime to abort a pregnancy solely because the fetus is female. In our country female foeticide has become a major problem in contemporary society. The Female foeticide is to be stopped then there has to be a restriction on all the persons involved in such evil practice like medical professionals, clinics, people in general and also people who sell ultrasound and other medicines. This paper will discuss the practice of Female foeticide in India and the consequences of women in Indian society.

Introduction

Female foeticide in India is the act of killing a Female fetus outside the legal channels of abortion; it occurs in India for assumed cultural reasons that span centuries. In India since from many decades after independence many Indians are still trapped in age-old traditional beliefs. Here, 'old beliefs' imply the mindset of people who still find themselves in the trap of male-female inequality. The status of females in India aptly symbolizes India's status of being a developing nation. India is a land of religion where a girl is seen as an incarnation of the goddess. In Indian society the birth of a girl child is often seen as a curse to the family and the child is considered as a burden. Some

people say that this belief was true in the past, but it is not true of the current modern times where the girls are given equal opportunity in education, work and other areas where they excel. Some may say that science, development, education and information have changed the way people think. Many families put pressure on women to give birth to a male baby than a female baby so that he can take the burden of the family and for the funeral pyre of his parents. But, we all know that the truth of the matter is that even today the position of the girl child is not very positive in various parts of the country. Among the rich and the poor, the birth of a girl is viewed as a bad thing and families will go to any extent to fulfill the wish of making a girl child. People are using advanced scientific techniques to find out the sex of the child in the womb and then aborting the fetus if they find the child is female. While science and technology development and education are making the world progressive for women, in reality, it is the same science which is being used by people to discriminate against women.

What is Female Foeticide?/A Pre-natal Diagnostic Test?

- Female foeticide is the practice of aborting a fetus when a person finds out that the fetus is female after undergoing a sex determination test known as prenatal diagnostic tests.
- A prenatal diagnostic test refers to detect abnormalities and defects in the fetus.

Methodology

Secondary data has been collected from the published sources such as various periodicals, articles, journals, reports and books on the issue.

Origin of Female Foeticide and Human Sex Ratio

Female foeticide started in the early 1990s of affordable ultrasound technology and its widespread adoption in India. Obstetric ultrasonography, either Trans vaginally or Trans abdominally, checks for various markers of fetal sex. It can be prepared at after 12 weeks of pregnancy according to a 2001 study. Accuracy for males is approximately 50% and for females almost 100% after 13 weeks of pregnancy, ultrasonography gives an accurate result in almost 100% cases. According to some scholar, 10 million female fetuses may have been illegally aborted in India since the 1990s and 5, 00,000 girls were being lost annually due to Female Foeticide. Macpherson estimates that 1, 00,000 abortions every year continue to be performed in India solely because the fetus is female.

According to William James and others Suggest that Conventional Assumption has been

- There are equal numbers of XX and XY chromosomes in mammalian sperms.
- X and Y stand an equal chance of achieving conception.
- Therefore equal numbers of male-female zygotes are formed.
- Variation of sex ratio at birth is due to sex selection between conception and birth.

Female Foeticide in India

In Indian society Female foeticide has emerged as a burning social problem during the last few Years. The girl child in India is treated right from her birth as an additional burden an extra mouth to feed and a liability and belong to others after marriage. Female Foeticide is perhaps one of the worst forms of violence against women where a woman is denied her most basic right, i.e., “the right of life.” Female Foeticide is not new in India this evil practice was there from the centuries. Female Foetuses are selectively eliminated after pre-natal sex determination before they are born. As a result of selective abortion between 35 and 40 million girls and women are missing from the Indian population. In some parts of the country, the sex ratio of girls to boys has dropped to less than 800:1000. The United Nations has expressed serious concern about the situation.

- The child sex ratio is within the natural range in all Eastern and Southern states of India.
- Higher in certain Western and North Western states such as Punjab, Haryana, Jammu and Kashmir.
- Western states of Maharastra and Rajasthan according to 2011 census found a child sex ratio of 113, Gujarat at 112 and where as Uttar Pradesh at 111.
- According to the Indian census data suggests there is a positive correlation between abnormal sex ratio and better socio-economic status and literacy status mainly because of the dowry system in India where dowry deaths occur when a girl is seen as a financial burden.
- Urban India has higher child sex ratio than rural India according to 1991, 2001 and 2011 census data.
- The child sex ratio greater than 115 boys per 100 girls is found in regions where the predominant majority is Hind, Muslim, Sikh or Christian.
- The normal child sex ratio of 104 to 106 boys per 100 girls is also found in regions where the predominant majority is Hindu, Muslim, Sikh or Christian. These data contradict any hypotheses may suggest that the sex selection is an archaic practice which takes place among uneducated, poor section or particular religion of the Indian society.

Rural Areas

In rural areas where most people do not have access to sex determination facilities the rate of female infanticide is alarming instead of female foeticide. 'Infanticide is the killing of a child after birth.' In India there are many shocking instances of female infanticide by strangulation, poisoning, dumping in garbage bins, drowning, burying alive, starvation and over exposure to elements.

Urban Areas

Surprising, but true is the fact that often educated and wealthy people in urban areas too nurse a desire for a male child. The only saving grace is that they may not kill their daughter after birth. These educated classes tend to misuse the technique of surgical termination of pregnancy to get rid of an unborn female child. They determine the sex of the child using ultrasound techniques and subsequently get rid of the female fetus using MTP.

The following table indicates the sex ratio of Females per 1000 males in India from (1901-2011) according to Census.

Year	Sex Ratio	Sex Ratio in children (0-6 years)
1901	972	-
1911	964	-
1921	955	-
1931	950	-
1941	945	-
1951	946	-
1961	941	976
1971	930	964
1981	934	962
1991	929	945
2001	933	927

- Census of India 2011 in India is now home to 17.5% of humanity, as the population touched 1.21 billion, up 17.4% from 2001, according to the provisional figures of 2011 census, a sharp downward trend, and fell 39% from 2001.

Reasons for Female Foeticide

- Various theories have been proposed as possible reasons for sex-selective abortion.
- Culture is favored by some researchers, while some favored disparate gender-biased access to resources.
- Female births may also be a reason for high sex ratios.
- Natural reasons may also explain some of the abnormal sex ratios.
- Desire to have sons because the son takes the family's name forward, light the funeral pyre and be the bread earner of the family.
- Dowry-people do not want to have girls because they will have to pay dowry at the time of their marriage.
- Two-child norm of some state governments has resulted in increased Female foeticide because if people are to have two children, they give more preference for boys.
- Sex determination tests are done easily and they are affordable.
- Abortion is easy to obtain.
- Due to unethical doctors and medical professionals have made it easy for Female foeticide to flourish.

Laws and Regulations

- The main laws on female foeticide covered the Indian penal code and pre-natal diagnostic techniques (prevention of sex selection) Act 1994 commended in 2002.
- Practices such as foeticide have been in India for centuries.
- The several provisions in the Indian penal code which make these practices a crime for ex. Section 314 IPC-if someone is trying to cause a miscarriage on women; this results in the death of the women; it is a crime and is punishable with imprisonment for 10 years or fine.
- The miscarriage is being performed without the consent of the women then the punishment could be life imprisonment.
- India passed its first abortion-related law, the so-called Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act of 1971, making abortion legal in most states, but specified legally acceptable reasons for abortion such as medical risk and rape.
- The law also established physicians who can legally provide the procedure and facilities where abortions can be performed but did not anticipate female foeticide based on technology advances.
- Increasing availability of sex screening technologies in India through the 1980s in Urban India and its misuse, the government of India passed the Pre-natal Diagnostic Techniques Act (PNDT) in 1994.
- PCPNDT (Pre-conception and Pre-natal Diagnostic Techniques) Regulation and prevention of misuse Act in 2004 to punish pre-natal sex screening and female foeticide.
- The parliament has passed the prenatal diagnostic techniques (Regulation and prevention of misuse) Act 1994; which came into force from 1996.
- Due to the impact of Indian laws on female foeticide and its enforcement is unclear, United Nations Population Fund and India's National Human Rights Commission, in 2009 asked the government of India to assess the impact of the law.
- The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare of India has targeted education and media advertisements to reach clinics and medical professionals to increase awareness.

- The Indian Medical Association has undertaken efforts to prevent prenatal sex selection by giving the members Beti Bachao (Save the Daughter).
- The government of India, in 2011 report better educating all stake holders about MTP and PCPNDT laws in its communication campaigns, it is clearly up public misconception by emphasizing sex determination is illegal, but abortion is legal on certain medical conditions in India.
- The Supreme Court directive of 2003 to State governments to enforce the law banning the use of sex determination technologies, the Ministry set up a National Inspection and Monitoring Committee (NIMC).
- The government is also supporting the implementation of programs and initiatives that seek to reduce gender discrimination including media campaign to address the social causes of sex selection.
- Recent policy initiatives adopted by many states of India claims Guilmoto, attempt to address the assumed economic disadvantages of girls by offering support to girls and their parents these policies provide cash and scholarships to girls.
- Some states are offering higher pension benefits to parents who raise one or two girls.
- India has been experimenting with various innovations in their girl-driven welfare policies for ex. The State of Delhi adopted a pro-girl policy initiatives (locally called Laadli Scheme).
- Aamir Khan devoted the first episode “Daughter is Precious” of his show Satyamev Jayate to raise awareness to this widespread practice, focusing primarily on Western Rajasthan, which is known to be one of the areas where this practice is common.
- The Mumbai High Court ruled that prenatal sex determination implied female foeticide. Sex determination violated a women’s right to live and against India’s constitution.
- Many celebrities in India have publicly supported the Beti Bachao Campaign.
- Any violation, including unlicensed lapse of the act, leads to seizure of equipment. The fine for those who indulge in sex selection procedure has been doubled from 50,000(fifty thousand) to 1, 00,000 (one lakh) with additional provisions for the suspension and cancellation of the registration of those as a medical practitioner by the concerned medical council or any other legal authority.

Conclusion

The problem of female foeticide is similar to child marriage, female infanticide, etc., everyone knows it is wrong and illegal but still they commit a mistake, because they think they will not be caught by the law. Female foeticide is a problem which has long term negative consequences on the lives of women; it affects not only the unborn girl child but has a very bad effect on the lives of women in general. The person who suffers at the end is the woman. A decrease in the number of women in the society increases violence against women such as forced marriages, bride selling, dowry demands, kidnapping for marriage, etc. In Rajasthan village, the women who exist are forced to marry several men. News paper reports say that in some parts of Haryana, men are buying brides from other states such as Assam and West Bengal because they are not able to find women to marry in their areas. For a healthy society like India, the male-female sex ratio must remain at a balanced level. The alarming rate of female foeticide is a cause of grave concern as the number of girls born is declining drastically in several sections of our society, due to this disproportionate ratio, the situation has the potential to expose females to more exploitation and violence. This state of affairs if not checked will have a disastrous impact on the future generations of our country. The person who indulges in such an evil practice of female foeticide must be punished according to the law. Stop killing an unborn baby.

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